

THE ROLE OF EDUCATIONAL GAMES IN TEACHING ENGLISH TO
YOUNG LEARNERS.

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Abstract: The age limit for starting English language teaching has been gradually reduced. As a rule, a four-year-old child is already considered fully ready for lessons. The possibilities of learning a foreign language at an early age are truly incomparable. Even K. D. Ushinsky wrote: "A child learns a foreign language in a few months more than we can learn in a few years." The main goal of education and training in the modern educational space is to form a comprehensively developed person, a well-rounded person. Teaching a foreign language at preschool age makes a unique contribution to the formation of such a personality. This article discusses the importance of action games in teaching English to preschool children.

Key words: linguistic games, small groups, sunflower game, blackboard, let's play together, idea.

Since learning foreign languages is gaining importance today, languages are taught not only in higher education institutions, schools, but also in pre-school educational institutions. If the lessons are not taught with unique and interesting methods, it can become a difficult task to attract students to the lesson. If traditional methods are used in the lessons, if they are conducted in an interesting way, this not only ensures the quality of the lesson, but also prevents boredom and attracts passive students to participate in the lesson. In today's rapidly developing education, we need advanced pedagogical technologies as well as advanced teachers in order to ignite the heart of students and develop it in every way. Learning and teaching is a long and perfect process. This requires regular work and self-improvement. It is clear that the use of various interactive methods in the process of teaching foreign languages for the development of oral speech skills turns language learning into an interesting and favorite activity.

Teaching a foreign language is a difficult task. Experts say that the role of interactive methods in teaching a foreign language is very important, because it motivates students and keeps their interest throughout the lesson. Interactive methods include games, songs, poems, activities. The main purpose of language learning is to communicate with foreigners, so teachers should first improve students' communication skills. For this, we need interactive methods, students can be involved in different games during the lesson, which provides language practice for different

skills - speaking, writing, listening and reading. Also, games improve students' vocabulary skills. Authors of many experienced textbooks and methodical manuals emphasize that games are not only time-filling activities, but also have great educational value. According to WR Lee, many language games force students to use the language instead of thinking about learning the correct forms. He also says that games should be seen as a central part of the foreign language teaching program, not a peripheral one. A similar opinion is expressed by Richard-Amato, who considers games to be interesting, but warns against neglecting their pedagogical value, especially in foreign language teaching. There are many benefits of using games. "Games can reduce anxiety, which increases the likelihood of gaining access" . They are very stimulating and interesting, and can give shy students more opportunities to express their thoughts and feelings. They also allow students to acquire new experiences in a foreign language, which is not always possible during a regular class. In addition, to quote Richard-Amato, they "add distraction to routine classroom activities," break the ice, "but they are also used to introduce new ideas." Students remember things faster and better in a comfortable, relaxed environment created by games. SM Silvers says that many teachers are enthusiastic about using games as "learning tools", but they often view games as mere time-fillers, "a break from the monotony of drill" or frivolous. are taken as actions. She notes that many teachers often ignore the fact that real learning takes place in a relaxed environment and that students use language they have encountered and practiced before. Games have advantages and effectiveness in learning vocabulary in different ways. First, games provide relaxation and fun for students, thus helping them learn and retain new words more easily. Second, games usually involve friendly competition and are engaging for students. These motivate English learners to engage and actively participate in learning activities. Third, vocabulary games bring real-world context into the classroom and enhance students' flexible, communicative use of English. Therefore, the role of games in teaching and learning vocabulary cannot be denied. However, to get the most out of vocabulary games, you need to choose the right games. When a game is to be played, the number of students, skill level, cultural context, time, learning topic, and classroom setting are factors to consider. "Learning vocabulary through games is one of the most effective and fun methods that can be used in any classroom.

All games or exercises in a foreign language open the way to the magical world of words. Therefore, I think that every person who wants to be a real foreign language teacher should be creative, i.e. adapt to the students' knowledge without always using the same games, and use their words every time. you can change, choose the appropriate one, create new ones, and generally make the lesson more interesting and enjoyable

with the help of these games. In such lessons and group activities, students never get bored and fully participate in the lesson, and at the same time look forward to the next lesson. Below, I would like to show some examples of the games that I use for my students who are learning English in my spare time, and I also recommend them to my peers who want to become teachers in the future: 1. In the game "Sunflower" students are divided into groups of 4-5 people. Based on the topic of the subject, the teacher poses one problem. Each group makes a sunflower, places a circle in its center and glues leaves. Depending on the topic, each group writes one general problem in a circle and sticks it on the blackboard. During the allotted time, the groups write their thoughts on a leaf and place it on a flower with that group's problem written on it. This method can be used to explain the subject, reinforce and repeat it, and determine the knowledge acquired by students. In our next game, the task will be performed in pairs. The first participant says his name in a foreign language, and the second participant says the name of his friend and adds his name to it. For example: First student: My name is Jeremie Second student: His name is Jeremie and my name is Nicole. and then the game continues like this. Such games can be played at the beginning of the school year with students who are just getting to know each other. Through this, they learn their names and their friends' names in English. What is your name? What is your hobby? and in the game, the participants sit in a circle. For this, you need a small soft ball. In this case, the leader throws the ball to one of the participants. The student who received the ball should say his name and talk about himself. Then he throws the ball to another participant. The student who fails to fulfill the condition leaves the game.

Conclusion: When using games, we can change them depending on the knowledge and age of children, that is, make them easier or more complicated. The purpose of these above-mentioned games is to strengthen the memory of students, increase their mental capacity, quickness, intelligence, remember new words easily and, most importantly, organize the lesson meaningfully. Today, the educational process is mainly carried out in a traditional way, but at all stages of the educational system, continuous learning of foreign languages, as well as improving the qualifications of teachers and teaching with modern educational and methodological materials provision requires further improvement. By introducing advanced methods of education with modern pedagogy and information communication, it is desirable to make the growing young generation an expert in the languages they are learning, and on the basis of this, they can speak these languages easily. After all, everything is for the great future of our youth and the development of our country.

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